

SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENTS IN ENGLISH FOR SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL

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Abstract

Introduction: Language ability information is important and necessary. Universities are unlikely to admit students without some understanding of their English competence or competency. The same can be said for companies that hire interpreters or translators. These entities certainly need dependable measures of language ability.

Methods: This descriptive research design aimed to develop summative assessments to address the least mastered competencies in English among Senior High School students based on the level of English competencies as perceived by the Senior High School English teachers and the problems encountered by teachers in teaching the English competencies. The study employed a validated questionnaire to gather data. The teacher respondents were selected using random sampling. Frequency and percentage were used to analyze the data.

Results: The study found out that teachers perceived learners to be at emerging level in listening competency, expanding level in reading, and viewing competency, and emerging level in writing competency. Moreover, all the English competencies were rated serious as to the problems encountered by teachers in teaching the English competencies.

Conclusions: Based on the results of the survey conducted to SHS English teachers, the following English language competencies, namely, reading, writing, and listening may be considered in the constructing of summative assessments. These English competencies were perceived by the teachers to have the lowest levels and contain weak points that need to be addressed through assessment tools. In like manner, serious cases of problems encountered in teaching these competencies may also be considered.

Keywords: Summative Assessments in English, English Language Competencies, Level of Language Competency, Problems Encountered, Competencies

Introduction

Knowledge about a person's linguistic prowess is crucial and essential. Colleges and universities are hesitant to accept students who cannot demonstrate at least basic proficiency in English. The same is true for businesses that need interpreters or translators. These organizations need accurate tests of language proficiency (McGregor & Yen, 2022).

There is a great potential for instructors and students to learn from one another in today's more varied classrooms. Considering the increasing number of students throughout the globe who are learning English as a second language, it is essential that both mainstream and resource instructors have a firm grasp on how to design and administer multilingual and multicultural literacy programs. In today's context of growing responsibility via student achievement on standardized exams, it is more important than ever to provide instruction in English to kids for whom English is a second language (Cairns, 2021).

Senior High School students must realize and be aware of their level of competencies to work further in coping with the demands of the curriculum exits, namely, business, college, midlevel training, and work. Likewise, examination is an important part of every teaching and learning experience. It helps teachers determine if the teaching process is effective. For the learners, it gives them a sense of accomplishment and requires them to study hard, showing them what skills, they need to master and what content they need to understand. Indeed, testing is an integral part of the evaluation process in education.

Since examinations are still considered useful, they will likely continue to be a focal point of the school system. Teachers may gauge whether their learners grasp concepts and information via the use of examinations. Tests that are both challenging and fair do a similar job of inspiring students and guiding them in the organization of their study time. According to studies mentioned by Walck-Shannon et al., (2021), including those by Sense et al., (2021), students tailor their study habits to the kind of questions they anticipate seeing on exams. If they think the test will be fact-based, they will cram for it; if they think it will assess their ability to solve problems or apply what they have learned, they will concentrate on doing the latter. Teachers might derive insights into the effectiveness of their lessons by analyzing student test results. Lastly, exams may help students learn more effectively by revealing which concepts and abilities they still need to work on.

At the conclusion of each marking period, teachers give their learners a final exam designed to assess how much they have learned over the course of the term. Summative assessments include a variety of test formats designed to gauge the mastery of certain competencies. Most instructors rely on this as the foundation for their final grade. However, there are theoretical requirements that must be met in the design of summative tests, including validity, reliability, objectivity, discriminating power, and practicality. Simply put, the validity of a test may be determined by doing a thorough analysis of its content to see whether it covers a sufficient subset of the intended behavioral area for assessment. In the same manner, a test is considered dependable if it provides a fair assessment of a student's abilities (Kanevsky et al., 2022).

Students, especially those in upper-level courses, need to be exposed to assessments that adhere to the essential guidelines in designing and constructing assessments, such as the language competencies that are tested and need to be mastered, because they will be taking standardized tests outside of the formal education setting, such as the Basic Education Exit Assessment, college entrance exams, government examinations, among others. Therefore, it is essential to design and introduce students to language proficiency assessments so that they are well-equipped for life beyond high school.

English is being used as a medium of instruction at the elementary, secondary, and postsecondary levels. Because English is not the country's original language, it is the educational system's job to prepare students to develop skills in hearing, speaking, reading, and

writing in other languages, notably English. Since it is difficult to compete in the global marketplace without some level of English ability, English is seen as a qualification rather than a foreign language to be taught (Hayes, 2022).

Piiranen-Marsh and Lilja (2022) also noted some problems that include funding and delay in the transport of instructional resources and materials and issues of pedagogy in language teaching. This time, English language instruction focused heavily on syntax and structure, prohibiting the usage of the first language, which is unavoidable for a non-native English speaker. Other drawbacks in language education, aside from pedagogical issues, include: short school sessions, fewer years of training, a lack of text and additional materials, a high number of unskilled teachers, big class sizes, and imprecise language models.

In literacy learning, listening, viewing, speaking, representing, writing, and reading are all interconnected cognitive and social activities. Through reading, observing, and hearing, students derive meaning from materials provided by others. Students use writing, speaking, and modeling to create meaning in order to communicate with others. None of the language arts can be totally separated from the others in real-life learning situations.

Enders et al., (2021) stressed that teachers should provide learners with worksheets involving quiz, questionnaire, and sentence stems to be completed, statements to be discussed and the four language skills exercises as today, language learning is seen as an activity which perceived students as complex human beings, and not simply as language learners. Students need practice in all skills in order to become efficient in the English language.

Moreover, Kloser et al., (2022) stated that in classrooms, teachers use tests to evaluate students' performance and see where they can adjust. This helps both the teacher and the learners to determine how much they have taught and learnt, respectively. Likewise, testing motivate students to learn. Under normal circumstances, then the date of either weekly or monthly test is announced by the subject teacher, serious students prepare adequately in order for them to pass with flying colors. It also encourages those who perform below par to study hard for them to pass the next test. Furthermore, testing gives teachers the opportunity to report to parents their children's progress.

Consequently, based on Chomsky's theory (Ayriza et al., 2020), linguistic competence is man's unconscious knowledge of languages and the organizing principles of a language. Therefore, linguistic competence refers to the knowledge and the ability of individuals for appropriate language use in the communicative events in which they find themselves in any particular speech community.

Furthermore, the theory of language testing, as Kansizoglu and Akdogdu (2022) asserts, assumes that language is a system of habits of communication. These habits permit the communicant to give his conscious attention to the over-all meaning he is conveying or perceiving. These habits involve matters of form, meaning, and distribution at several levels of structure namely those of the sentence, clause, phrase, word, morpheme, and phoneme.

With these arguments, this research was anchored on these theories as tests should reflect effective use of the language. To achieve the very purpose of testing, that is to translate educational goals to good tests, these must be designed in consistency with addressing the target competencies and objectives.

Research Problems

This study investigated the English competencies of learners and problems of teachers in teaching these competencies in English Senior High School classes of the Schools Division of Ilocos Norte as basis of developing of summative assessments. Specifically, it sought to probe the following questions: (1) What is the level of competencies of Senior High School students in English as perceived by the SHS English teachers as to listening, reading, and viewing; and writing?; (2) What are the problems encountered by teachers in teaching English

competencies in terms of listening, reading, writing; and viewing?; and (3) What intervention can be recommended to enhance the competencies of students in English?

Methods

Research Design. This study utilized the descriptive research design. It determined the level of competencies in English language of SHS students as perceived by the Senior High School English teachers of Bacarra, San Nicolas, Sarrat, and Vintar, Ilocos Norte. It further identified the problems encountered by English teachers in teaching the English language competencies. The results of which were the bases in developing the summative assessments as intervention tool in addressing the low level of competencies and problems in teaching them to students.

Participants. The research was conducted at the Department of Education Schools Division of Ilocos Norte. The Division is clustered into districts and these districts are combined into units. There are five (5) units in the Division of Ilocos Norte. In particular, the study investigated the level of English competencies of SHS students from the Central Unit of the Schools Division of Ilocos Norte. There are two (2) public secondary schools in Bacarra, two (2) in San Nicolas, three (3) in Sarrat, and five (5) in Vintar. Total enumeration was used in identifying the sample of the study. Thus, all SHS English teachers in the Central Unit was used as sample. In total, there were twenty-three 23 SHS English teachers who served as respondents of the study.

Research Instrument. A survey questionnaire was given to the SHS English teachers to determine the level of competencies and the problems encountered in teaching the English language competencies. The survey questionnaire was divided into two parts: the level of English competencies of SHS; and the problems encountered by the teachers in teaching the English competencies. In identifying the level of English competencies, questions were adapted from the Stages of English Language Proficiency standards developed by Teaching English to Speakers of Other Languages (TESOL). Likewise, the problems encountered by teachers in teaching the English competencies were determined in the second part of the survey questionnaire adapted from the interview questions by Alnahigh and Altalhab (2019). Some modifications were incorporated to be able to adjust to the needs and purpose of this study.

Data Collection. The study was governed by the following stages in the collection of pertinent data. First, the researcher requested for the conduct of gathering data to SHS English teachers from the Schools Division of Ilocos Norte (SDOIN) – Superintendent’s Office.

Second, after the granting of request by the Superintendent, the researcher coordinated through online messaging and/or personally give letter of request to the school heads of the different secondary schools in the Central Unit of the SDOIN.

Third, the researcher conducted the survey to SHS English teachers in the Central Unit on the perceived level of English language competencies and problems encountered in teaching the English language competencies. Online survey was used and questionnaire was transformed to Google Forms considering the restrictions brought about by the present pandemic.

Finally, the results were analyzed as bases for designing and constructing table of specifications along with the summative assessments as intervention material in addressing the weak points or low level of English competencies and the serious problems in teaching the language competencies.

Data Analysis. The data gathered from the administration of the survey questionnaire to teachers in identifying the level of English competencies of SHS students as perceived by the SHS English teachers were analyzed using frequency count. The level of competency was determined with the range of values as the following:

Level	Descriptive Interpretation
5	Bridging
4	Expanding
3	Developing
2	Emerging
1	Starting

Moreover, the problems encountered in teaching the English competencies were analyzed using weighted mean with the range of values as follows:

Range of Means	Descriptive Interpretation
3.51 – 4.50	Strongly Agree (SA)
2.51 – 3.50	Agree (A)
1.51 – 2.50	Disagree (D)
1.00 – 1.50	Strongly Disagree (SD)

Results

This part of the paper presents the analysis and interpretation of results of data gathered anchored on the research problems.

Level of English Competencies of Senior High School Students as Perceived by SHS English Teachers

Table 1 presents the perception of the SHS English teachers as respondents on the level of English competencies of SHS students.

Table 1

Level of English Competencies of Senior High School Students as Perceived by SHS English Teachers

English Competencies	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Listening (Students...)		
Level 1: understand phrases and short sentences using familiar vocabulary.	3	13.04
Level 2: can understand basic instructions or take part in a basic factual conversation on a predictable topic.	6	26.09
Level 3: may understand and use some specialized academic vocabulary.	5	21.74
Level 4: may have difficulty understanding and using some idioms, figures of speech, and words with multiple meanings.	5	21.74
Level 5: can contribute effectively to meetings within own area of work or cope with abstract expressions.	4	17.39
Level of Competency		2 (Emerging)
Reading/Viewing (Students...)		
Level 1: construct meaning from text primarily through non-print features (e.g., illustrations, graphs, maps, tables).	1	4.35
Level 2: locate specific, predictable information in simple everyday or environmental print.	7	30.43
Level 3: can read quickly enough to cope with an academic course, to read the media for information or to understand non- standard correspondence	2	8.70
Level 4: may read independently but may have occasional comprehension problems, especially when processing grade-level information.	12	52.17
Level 5: make minimal errors that are difficult to spot or are generally corrected when they occur	1	4.35
Level of Competency		4 (Expanding)
Writing (Students...)		
Level 1: surface features and rhetorical patterns of the native language (such as replication of ways of structuring text from native culture and language)	1	4.35
Level 2: write for themselves to express their own personality and personal thoughts.	8	34.78
Level 3: texts still containing a considerable number of unconventional features.	6	26.09
Level 4: make errors in one or more domains that generally do not interfere with communication	6	26.09

Level 5: can produce clear, smoothly flowing, well-structured texts of differing lengths and degrees of linguistic complexity.	2	8.70
Level of Competency		2 (Emerging)

Legend:

Level	Descriptive Interpretation
5	Bridging
4	Expanding
3	Developing
2	Emerging
1	Starting

Table 1 shows that as to listening competency, students are at Level 2 emerging with six (6) responses at 26.09%. This is followed by Level 3 and Level 4 with five (5) responses at 21.74% each. Level 5 and Level 1 come next with four (4) responses at 17.39% and five (5) responses at 13.04%, respectively.

The table also shows the reading/viewing competency of SHS students. It is shown that majority of the teacher respondents perceived students to have Level 4 expanding reading and viewing competency with twelve (12) responses at 52.17%; followed by Level 2 with seven (7) responses at 30.43%; Level 3 with two (2) responses at 8.70%; Level 1 and Level 5 with one (1) response at 4.35% each.

Table 1 further shows that the student's writing competency is at Level 2 emerging with eight (8) responses at 34.78%; followed by Level 3 and Level 4 with six (6) responses at 26.09% each; Level 5 with two (2) responses at 8.70%; and Level 1 with one (1) response at 4.35%.

Problems Encountered by SHS Teachers in Teaching the English Competencies

Table 2 shows the problems encountered by SHS teachers in teaching the English competencies.

Table 2

Problems Encountered by SHS Teachers in Teaching English Competencies

Problems Encountered	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
Listening		
1. Inability to perform adequate listening practices	2.83	Serious
2. Lack of concentration, apathy, anxiety, lack of knowledge, prejudice, and inattention	2.96	Serious
3. Lack of quality listening materials	2.78	Serious
4. Different accents in listening materials or text, lack of standards in the speed of speech	2.78	Serious
5. Lengthy listening materials/text, complicated contents, and lack of visuals	2.87	Serious
Composite Mean	2.84	Serious
Reading		
1. Deficiencies in textbooks and other reading materials	2.74	Serious
2. Lack of vocabulary, and grammar knowledge	2.83	Serious
3. Inability to attribute meaning to texts (including limited schema or prior knowledge about a text)	3.00	Serious
4. Lack of retention and difficulty answering comprehension questions	2.87	Serious
5. Difficulties in making inferences.	2.87	Serious
6. Difficulties in getting the main idea and understanding explicit information.	2.74	Serious
Composite Mean	2.84	Serious
Writing		
1. Lack of motivational factors	2.87	Serious
2. Difficulty in organizing thoughts in correct way	3.04	Serious
3. Insufficient grammar knowledge, vocabulary, spelling, and mechanics	2.91	Serious

4. Lack of activities related to the development and acquisition of writing skills in textbooks	2.57	Serious
5. Differences between sentence structures in Filipino, mother tongue, and English	2.70	Serious
Composite Mean	2.82	Serious
Viewing		
1. Limited prior knowledge about a topic or theme	2.78	Serious
2. Lack of opportunity to create and respond to visual texts	2.70	Serious
3. Lack of or limited graphics/pictures in textbooks and other learning materials	2.74	Serious
4. Limited technology skills	2.61	Serious
5. Limited narrative analysis skills (ability to recall and recognize what happen and why, with reference to genre codes and conventions)	2.91	Serious
6. Difficulty comparing and contrasting media representations in reality	2.61	Serious
Composite Mean	2.72	Serious
Overall Mean	2.80	Serious

Legend:

<i>Range of Means</i>	<i>Descriptive Interpretation</i>
3.51 – 4.50	Very Serious (SA)
2.51 – 3.50	Serious (A)
1.51 – 2.50	Slightly Serious (D)
1.00 – 1.50	Not Serious (SD)

As shown in Table 2, all the English competencies were rated “Serious” with overall mean of 2.80. However, of the five competencies, the problems mostly encountered are with listening and reading with composite mean of 2.84 for both competencies. These are followed by writing with 2.82 composite mean; and viewing with composite mean of 2.72.

As to listening, teacher respondents agree that lack of concentration, apathy, anxiety, lack of knowledge, prejudice, and inattention is the main problem encountered with 2.96 (Serious) weighted mean. This is followed by lengthy listening materials/text, complicated contents, and lack of visuals with (2.87) “Serious” weighted mean; and inability to perform adequate listening practices with (2.83) “Serious” weighted mean.

Moreover, as to reading, problem on inability to attribute meaning to texts including limited schema or prior knowledge about a text is mostly encountered by teachers with 3.00 (Serious) weighted mean. This is followed by lack of retention and difficulty answering comprehension questions and difficulties in making inferences with 2.87 (Serious) weighted mean for each of the variable.

As regard to writing competency, teacher respondents claim that students have difficulty in organizing thoughts in correct way with 3.04 (Serious) weighted mean. This is followed by insufficient grammar knowledge, vocabulary, spelling, and mechanics with 2.91 (Serious) weighted mean; and lack of motivational factors with 2.87 (Serious) weighted mean.

Furthermore, there is limited narrative analysis skills (ability to recall and recognize what happen and why, with reference to genre codes and conventions) is the main problem encountered in teaching viewing with weighted mean of 2.91 (Serious). This is followed by limited prior knowledge about a topic or theme with 2.78 (Serious) weighted mean; and lack of or limited graphics/pictures in textbooks and other learning materials with 2.74 (Serious) weighted mean.

Discussions

The teacher respondents categorized the listening competency of students as Level 2 emerging which describes students to understand basic instructions and can take part in a basic factual conversation on a predictable topic.

This goes to show that students can understand listening texts with familiar vocabularies and familiar sounds used in the academic setting but may be challenged when faced with real world listening engagements especially for second language learners. It is

highly evident that intervention material is needed in order to improve the listening competency of the students since they are still at emerging level. It is also evident that there are still students who belong to starting level, which means they are only able to understand phrases and short sentences using familiar vocabulary. Thus, as pointed out by Caruso et al., (2017) they need to be exposed to a wide variety of listening materials and integrate them in assessment procedures.

With the reading/viewing competency of SHS students, majority of the teacher respondents perceived students to have Level 4 or “Expanding” competency though there were still students who belong to Level 2 (Emerging) and Level 1 (Starting). Generally, students may read independently but may have occasional comprehension problems, especially when processing grade-level information (Murray, 2019).

Students can read quickly enough to cope with an academic course, to read the media for information or to understand non-standard correspondence and may read independently but may have occasional comprehension problems, especially when processing grade-level information. Similarly, there are still students perceived that belong to “Starting Level” who can only construct meaning from the text through non-print features such as illustrations, graphs, maps, and tables. Hence, intervention should be done to address the gaps between the level of competencies in reading and viewing (Nilsson, 2021).

The student’s writing competency is at Level 2 (Emerging) which describes learners as able to write only for themselves to express their own personality and personal thoughts. Some students though are still at Level 1 (Starting) which they have structure and rhetorical patterns issues in writing.

It is derived from the result that students need intervention as majority belongs to “Emerging” level and the presence of students perceived who still belongs to the “Starting” level where structures and rhetorical patterns of the native language is carried over in English writing discourses. Therefore, students need to work more on structures and patterns. Teachers need to expose them into wide variety of written texts and integrate such in constructing assessments (Primor & Katzir, 2018).

All the English competencies were rated “Serious” as to the problems encountered by teachers in teaching the English competencies. However, of the four competencies, the problems encountered most are with listening and reading competencies. These are followed by writing and viewing. As to speaking, teachers encountered serious problems with students’ lack of confidence in speaking due to anxiety, fear, shame, insecurity, shyness, excitement, unwillingness, embarrassment. As to listening, teacher respondents have serious problems with students’ lack of concentration, apathy, anxiety, lack of knowledge, prejudice, and inattention. This is followed by lengthy listening materials/text, complicated contents, and lack of visuals; and inability to perform adequate listening practices. As to reading, serious problems on inability to attribute meaning to texts including limited schema or prior knowledge about a text is serious problem encountered by teachers. This is followed by lack of retention and difficulty answering comprehension questions and difficulties in making inferences. As regards writing competency, teacher respondents claim that students have serious problems in organizing thoughts in correct way. This is followed by insufficient grammar knowledge, vocabulary, spelling, and mechanics, and lack of motivational factors. There are limited narrative analysis skills (ability to recall and recognize what happen and why, with reference to genre codes and conventions) is the serious problem encountered in teaching viewing. This is followed by limited prior knowledge about a topic or theme, and lack of or limited graphics/pictures in textbooks and other learning materials.

Knowing the problems faced by learners in reading, listening and comprehension is crucial for several reasons. First, is identification and assessment of weaknesses. Understanding the specific difficulties faced by learners in these areas can help educators identify the weaknesses in a learner's skills and tailor their teaching methods accordingly

(Kasani & Mourkani, 2020). This can lead to more effective learning and better outcomes. Second, is targeted intervention. Knowing the problems faced by learners in these areas can help educators provide targeted interventions that specifically address these difficulties (Machera, 2017). This can include things like providing additional support, modifying teaching methods, or recommending additional resources. Third, is improved learning outcomes. By addressing the problems faced by learners in reading, listening and comprehension, educators can help learners to improve their skills and achieve better learning outcomes (Alghonaim, 2020). This can lead to increased confidence, motivation, and success in their academic pursuits. Finally, better preparation for life skills. Reading, listening, and comprehension skills are important life skills that are needed for success in school and in the workplace (Keyser, 2021). By addressing these difficulties, learners can be better prepared for success in all areas of their lives.

Finally, knowing the problems faced by learners in reading, listening and comprehension is critical for effective teaching and improved learning outcomes. It is important for educators to be proactive in identifying and addressing these difficulties to help learners reach their full potential (Terada, 2019).

Conclusion

Based on the study's key results, the researchers infer that teachers at SHS saw their students' proficiency in English as developing in the areas of listening and writing and growing in the areas of reading. Furthermore, the SHS students now are in a more advanced grade of high school, who need even greater improvements to the skills. The incapacity of students to attach meaning to texts due to factors such as insufficient schema and previous information of a book in reading has been identified as a major challenge for English instructors when attempting to impart these skills to their students. When writing, they also struggle with constructing logical arguments. Moreover, while instructing viewers, it is important to address the issue of students' inadequate narrative analysis abilities, which include their lack of recollection and recognition of what happened and why, in relation to genre standards and conventions.

Recommendations

Considering the study's results and interpretations, the authors suggest the following: (1) Educators may include the English language competencies or macro skills into their lessons. As a result, the functions of language are continuous; (2) Assessments may be used in the future to gauge pupils' English language proficiency and tailor instruction accordingly; (3) Since this research relied on surveys from educators, more research on learners' English language abilities may be undertaken utilizing exams; (4) The findings may be used as a benchmark for developing curriculum and improvement policies in English; (5) Based on the findings, summative exams might be constructed to familiarize students with language test processes and topics; students may then utilize some of the information in classroom activities to better their English language skills; (6) the tests may be given out to teachers as a model or guide for creating their own tests, and they could be included into test banks.

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